

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INTERACTIVE METHODS AND SPEAKING PROFICIENCY

*M. Haydarova*¹

Abstract:

The article investigates relationship between interactive methods and speaking proficiency.

Key words: interactive methods, methodological skills, speaking skills, interactive games, skills-based tasks.

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Teaching young learners is always a challenge and requires new sophisticated approaches and solutions in terms of developing speaking skills. Interactive applied sciences of instructing foreign languages are based totally on activity-based method and comprise the use of interactive teaching methods, along with non-situational (dialogue) and situational (game, simulation, evaluation of situations, auction ideas, etc.); natural mixture in the academic process. It gives the threat to the teachers to make their gaining knowledge of session a complete lot of fun. They can make things a little competitive, can help college students analyze thru interactive games, and add tiers of achievement, which college students are sure to discover attractive. Applying interactive schooling has usually been a vital and tough part of instructing period.

Team-based interactive learning activities allow employees to form relationships as they problem-solve together. Working collaboratively with peers can make one see an issue from an angle they would not have thought of on their own, making for a richer learning experience. Engaging different learning styles. Engaging students through interactive activities, discussions, feedback and AI-enhanced technologies resulted in improved academic performance compared to traditional lectures, lessons or readings, faculty concluded after collecting research into active learning. Interactive means that people work together and have an influence on each other. This situation implies dialogue or conversation. Therefore, these methods aimed at the interaction between not only students and the teacher but also, with each other, it requires an active role of students in the learning process. The purpose of the interactive learning is to create the special conditions leading to the involvement of all students in the learning process when the participants can understand and realize everything that happens, influence each other and make their own contribution having established the friendly and mutually supportive relationship. Interactive activities and methods play a great role during the classes nowadays because as it is clear that children and any-level learners can easily be bored with doing something and interaction and communication skills-based tasks give them a chance to collaborate and socialize with others and motivate them to express and describe their ideas and thoughts promptly and gradually. At the beginning of the lesson, you should not explain the whole topic itself as a teacher or organizer of the class, you should try to engage students to the

¹ *Haydarova Maftuna Narzilla qizi, Master student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign languages*

class and topic and encourage them to be active and be in the center of the lesson. It is becoming more technical and modern period in education system as well and it requires us as a teacher to create new ways of teaching and implement practical classes more. Such kind of student-centered lessons will be more productive and effective for students' future career development and personal language skills. While implementing interactive methods and activities, there are several criteria and features that teachers should be more careful and intelligent. First and the most important thing is language awareness, teachers should have fluent and coherent language, correct pronunciation and self-confidence. Language awareness is how to know and use the language promptly and perfectly during the classes, as it known that there is a special way of using the language during the classes as a classroom language, and teachers are teaching the language, students are imitating to their teachers. Teachers are role models for students. Interactive educating is all about instructing the college students in a way they are actively worried with their learning process. There are exclusive ways to create an involvement like this. The following examples are the most important ones:

- teacher-student interaction;
- student-student interaction;
- the use of audio, visuals, video;
- physical demonstrations and exercises.

This endeavor gives students exercise with goal verbs and English syntax. It used with snap shots or with study room situations the teacher creates. Call a volunteer to the front of the type and whisper a command to the student. For example, tell the scholar to sit down and seem at a book. Ask the different college students to tell you what the volunteer is doing via presenting them a choice for a response. For example: "Is the boy standing up or sitting down?" Use pantomime moves to ensure that college students understand the question. If college students respond with one or two words (sitting; sitting down), verify appropriate work and encourage elaboration. "Yes, the boy is sitting down." Write the sentence on the board and have college students repeat it after you. Expand the exercise by giving students some other choice. For example, "What else is the boy doing? Is the boy searching at a e book or writing?" Again, use pantomime actions as needed. The innovative strategies also deal with this process and their goal is to evaluate the things to do of a teacher and beginners the usage of new approaches and strategies of educating along with new technical potential of teaching. As we know that methodological approach in teaching foreign languages might also be divided into three groups. They are Passive methods, Active techniques and interactive methods. If we speak right here in the first region about the passive methods, it has to be cited that in Passive strategies a trainer is in the center of teaching. He/ She performs active position but the learners are passive. Control can be carried out by the way of questions, person and manage work, assessments etc. It can also be useful when it used via an experienced teacher. Secondly, in Active methods rookies are also active. Their role and pastime are equal in the manner of interaction. Learners may also ask questions; categorical their ideas with a teacher. The ultimate however it is in the first in modern time interactive technique or method is a modernized form of energetic methods. The most of instructors typically recognize or imply cooperative motion at some point of the lesson. However, here interest be centered on inner motion too. The newcomers ought to have inner motivation includes them into lively work or active participation at the lesson. Listening and comprehension are difficult for beginners due to the fact they need to discriminate speech sounds quickly, keep them whilst listening to a word, a phrase or a sentence and apprehend this as a sense unit. Pupils can effortlessly and naturally do this in their personal language

and they cannot do this in a foreign language when they start studying the language. Pupils are very slow in greedy what they hear due to the fact they are conscious of the linguistic varieties they become aware of by means of the ear. These outcomes in misunderstanding or a complete failure of understanding. When speak-me and listening overseas language, scholars ought to be very attentive and suppose hard. We have to distinguish speech and oral workouts for they regularly blended up with the aid of the teacher. Speech is a method of conversation via capacity of language. For example, a pupil tells the category a story about a thing as soon as took place to him. The teacher asks questions on the story study by way of the students at domestic and begins a discussion. Pupils communicate on the snap shots cautioned by using the teacher, everyone tries to say what others have no longer mentioned; pupils listen to the story and get some new facts from the text; they see a sound movie and examine about something new from it. Oral workouts used for the pupils to assimilate phonetics, grammar and vocabulary.

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